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A machine learning approach for maintenance prediction of railway assets

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Abstract

With the shift from manual to computerized solutions, many railway agencies are storing and managing the immense amount of data relating to assets' properties and their operational performance. Yet, the maintenance of these assets is still driven by available budgets, planned schedules, experts' intuition, and abrupt failures. Railway agencies are lacking automated solutions that could make use of the available data and could assist in decision-making processes related to maintenance planning. In this paper, we try to limit this gap by making use of machine learning approaches on to harness the data. We trained two machine-learning classifiers on the dataset of points and crossings with the aim to predict their maintenance need and specific maintenance treatment. Based on the ensemble approach, random forest classifier obtained 87% accuracy in predicting maintenance need and 83% accuracy to predict maintenance treatment. The main contribution of this paper is, in using the data generated from well-known SAP ERP system, to develop classifiers that are able to assist infrastructure managers in future maintenance decision-making.

Keywords: machine learning; data analysis; railway assets; predict maintenance; classification

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1. Introduction

The ability to record, store and manage the immense amount of data have opened new horizons for the smart operations, management, and maintenance of transport infrastructure. The outlook of computerized solutions for timetable management, schedule planning, and resource management of transport is quite apparent (for example see Mazzarello & Ottaviani (2007); Turner, et. al, (2016)). However, the maintenance of transport infrastructure is still outmoded, where maintenance activities are derived by available budgets, planned schedules, experts' intuition, and abrupt failures. To make the optimal use of available and often limited resources, predictive maintenance is one of the most effective maintenance strategy. Predictive maintenance previously known as condition-based maintenance mainly rely on inspection and condition assessment of an asset to plan maintenance activities. The state of a deteriorating asset, which must sustain a certain level of performance, signals or triggers the appropriate timing for repairs treatment, thus avoiding unplanned downtime, abrupt failures and undue maintenance. Since, inspection and condition assessment of assets is a periodic process, it generates enormous amount of data overtime. Due to this, a decision maker or an infrastructure manager has to decide on multiple aspects of planning. For instance, should a maintenance be performed or can it be delayed? If maintenance is executed, then, which treatment is most appropriate considering the problem reported? When was maintenance performed last time? Can the maintenance be clustered with other collocating assets? When is the best time to perform the maintenance treatment while the network availability would be affected the least? etc. Theoretically, a decision maker must not only take into account these multiple attributes such as problem type, problem cause, condition state, design state of an object, etc., but should also consider the previous states of an asset and budget limitations while responding to aforementioned decision questions.

Driven from the need to process and use of large datasets, Machine Learning (ML) approaches are providing promising solutions in almost every industry (Bose & Mahapatra, 2001; Obermeyer & Emanuel, 2016). The supervised ML approaches concern about developing models that are able to learn from historical data, past experience and can predict future demands. For instance, to predict the failure of an asset, historical data of inspection and condition assessment can be used to train a ML classifier on the data points of functioning state and failing state to predict the future state of an asset. Similarly, ML algorithms are able to approximately learn the underlying data distribution, which can be used to solve many practical problems such as, sentiment analysis, outlier detection and time series forecasting etc. These models can act as a facilitator for a decision maker to aid-in decision-making process e.g. by predicting the maintenance need of assets in advance. For explanation of different machine learning algorithms, a reader can refer to (Bishop, 2006).

Few ML solution for predictive maintenance of assets has been reported in the literature. De Bruin, et al., (2017) used the recurrent neural networks to identify and detect the failures in railway track circuits by using the signals from multiple track circuits. Li et al., (2014) developed the failure prediction models using heterogonous type of data i.e. failure data, maintenance data, inspection schedule data, etc. to improve the overall railway network velocity. Similarly, Kauschke, et al., (2014) used the diagnostic log data to predict the component failure of a train. Moreover, efforts are being made to make use of diverse sources of data to extract relevant events and useful historical information (Nunez, et al, 2015). Without the use of ML models, it is intractable for a decision maker to even consider all the inspection and condition data of a single asset, let alone the data from heterogeneous resources for a number of assets.

In this paper, two ML classifiers are developed to fully exploit the available objective data of asset's condition and properties, accompanied by the specific inspection and maintenance procedures for the overall planning and prediction of maintenance need. These ML models are aimed to aid-in the decision-making process for infrastructure managers during maintenance planning procedure. To illustrate it, the data from points and crossings from a railway agency is used. The main contribution of this study is in developing ML models to predict the maintenance need and type of maintenance treatment based on the asset's properties, condition state, detected maintenance needs, past decisions, and details of previous maintenance treatments. We used the data mainly generated from maintenance request process from SAP Enterprise Resources Planning (ERP) system. SAP ERP system integrates various processes of a company and yields analytics and efficiency (SAP, 2017). The rest of the paper is structured as follows: the maintenance request process, details of datasets, and basic data analysis are provided in Section 2. A summary of ML classifiers that are used in this study is provided in Section 3. Section 4 presents the experiment details and results obtained for predicting maintenance need and maintenance treatment. Section 5 provides a detailed discussion on the results obtained and the potential of using ML approaches on available data of railway agencies. Finally, Section 6 provides the conclusion of this study.

2. Maintenance Request Process and Datasets

2.1. Maintenance Request Process

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system is being used in many railway agencies which enforces the data collection and collaboration processes. These systems were mostly implemented around a decade ago to leverage the computer technology for data storage and processing. Since then, many asset management organizations[†] are using these systems, which are marketed and implemented by many popular software vendors. In this paper, the data generated as a result of maintenance request process (referred as notification), implemented by SAP ERP work order management system is used to develop machine learning (ML) classifiers. The classifiers will be able to predict when the maintenance of an asset is needed as well as to predict type of maintenance treatment based on work-request. The models are trained on the data of Points and Crossings (P&C).

Figure 1 shows the maintenance request process implemented in SAP ERP. This system maintains a detailed inventory of each asset on the network, which includes asset's location, age, angle, material, etc. The (visual) inspection process is performed periodically to check the condition of an asset. In case, an asset is found in need of maintenance, the inspecting engineer creates a *notification* in the system. The created *notification* details the problem type, problem description and specification, and the possible solution. Once the *notification* is created, the maintenance engineer has to make a decision, should a maintenance be performed or can be delayed based on the information provided in a *notification*. In case, the decision is not to do any maintenance, further actions e.g. under-observation of additional condition monitoring are suggested and notification status is changed to completed. If the decision is made to perform the maintenance, then a *work-order* is created. Considering the problem defined in the *notification*, a decision on the type of maintenance treatment is made. Finally, the work-order is assigned to the maintenance plans, and the maintenance of an asset is performed. The data of *notifications*, *work-orders* and the decisions made are stored in the system. Therefore, for a single asset number of *notifications* and *work-orders* are generated over the years. This provides an opportunity to develop ML classifiers that could automate and assist maintenance engineers in deciding about asset's maintenance need (or planning) based on the notification properties and decisions taken in the past. This is highlighted in Figure 1 with the decision diamonds and bold-text questions.

Figure 1: Maintenance Request Process implemented in SAP ERP

2.2. Datasets

Following the explanation of a maintenance request process by which data is collected, in this section the description of the dataset is provided. As mentioned earlier, we used the point and crossing (P&C) data provided by a railway agency. Following four data sources are used to develop the classifiers for P&C maintenance:

- I. *Asset register* file provides the basic details of **825** P&Cs, which includes attributes like functional location, year of installation, P&C direction, object type, technical details, etc.
- II. The *condition data* file provides the most up-to-date information regarding the P&C condition state. A scorecard represents the condition state, where, 1 represents the good condition state and 4 represents the

[†] A quick google search suggest that Indian, UAE, Russian, Bulgarian, Irish, and Croatian railways are among those agencies that have implemented SAP ERP.

- poor condition state. The condition data file consist of three main features only i.e. unique identification number of P&C, condition assessment date and condition state (represented from 1-4).
- III. The *notifications* file consists of 10,913 notifications (i.e. maintenance request) that are generated for **825** P&C from 2010 to 2016. As discussed earlier, each notification is created after an inspection and provides the details of problem type, problem description and specification, and possible solution. On average, 12 notifications are created for a single P&C over 6 years. With the acceptance of a notification/maintenance request, a corresponding work-orders is created.
 - IV. The *work-orders* file consists of maintenance treatments triggered by planned maintenance and notification. It contains 10,000 observations, which include the details of chosen maintenance treatment, work order type and a link to the maintenance plan.

It is important to note that, all four of these data sources are inter-linked with unique P&C identification code, notification code and work-order code. These codes have helped us to trace back the decisions made in past to determine, if the maintenance was performed or not because of a notification. The notification file, in addition to its own unique code, includes the unique work-order code to show the assigned work treatment in the subsequent work-order file. Based on this specification, we labeled the data for training supervised ML models in following way:

- For all the notifications where work-order unique code was filled-in, the data was labeled as 1, meaning that maintenance was performed.
- Otherwise, notifications without filled-in work-order unique code assigned a label of 0, indicating that maintenance was not performed.

To classify maintenance treatment, no additional labeling of data was performed as performed maintenance treatment were already clearly stated in work-order file. The classifiers are then trained on the labeled data to first predict, if maintenance is performed or not and later to predict the type of maintenance treatment.

2.3. Exploratory data analysis

To provide a quick glance over the used data, the details of data analysis is provided in this section. Before analysis of data, the tasks of data munging were performed, which include renaming data variables to make them easy to understand, conversion of data types, merging dataset by various attributes e.g. by unique P&C identification code, notification code, or work-order code and handling the missing data values.

Most of the P&C (825 in total) lie within the age range of 5 to 25 years. We have eliminated the data of 11 P&Cs which don't have condition state data. Overall, P&C were found to have very good condition state represented by condition score 1. Figure 2 provides a box-and-whisker plot outlining the age of P&C with respect to their condition state. Each box with corresponding whisker represents the total spread of condition score relative to their age. While, the rectangle shows the median along with 2nd and 3rd quartile data range. P&Cs with condition score 1 have date range between 10 to 20 years of P&C age, while there is long spread of data over all ages. Age ranges for condition score 2 and 3 seems more relevant as an older P&C is more likely to have bad condition state. Expect for the outliers, at conditions score 3 the median age range of P&C is very high as compared to others because of deteriorating asset condition over the time. Though, it is important to consider the general data distribution, in which we had 25 times more data points with condition score 1 compared with condition score 3 as shown over each error bar in the graph.

Figure 2: Correlation between P&C condition score and age

With each of the notification generated for maintenance request, number of details such as identified problem, details of problem, specific components, and reason of the problem is stated. As discussed earlier, based on these details, an infrastructure manager decides if a maintenance should be performed or can be delayed. To provide an overview of the problems identified during inspection, frequency plots in Figure 3 and 4 are presented.

Among other identified problems of P&C, Figure 3 provides the details of the top 10 problems that are most frequently identified during inspection. In other words, these are the type of problems at P&C that trigger the need of maintenance. Figure 4 provides the details of problem specification or most frequent reasons of identified problems. Life cycle deterioration is one of the main reason of the problems identified in P&C. In addition, among the various components of P&C such as nose, switch rail, joints, etc., the most of the problem identified are at the switch panel. While, in contrast crossing panel is at number 6th and least problematic components are fish plate and gauge plate.

Figure 3: Top 10 of most frequently identified problems

Figure 4: Top 10 most frequent problem reasons

A number of different maintenance treatments for P&C have been introduced by railway agency. Among the list of 22 different maintenance treatments, we found only seven maintenance treatments that are mostly referred in the work-order data file. This is because, the maintenance treatments have different level of details e.g. being very detailed as oiling or greasing of joints to very general as P&C maintenance only. Further explanation of considered maintenance treatments is outlined in Section 4.2.

3. Machine learning algorithms/classifiers

The primary aim of machine learning is to make sense of complex and large data sources in order to do pattern recognition. Machine learning algorithms are achieving state-of-the-art results in several practical applications. For instance, filtering spam emails, predicting customers' preferences, determining election outcomes, development of self-driving cars, and targeted marketing. Different specialized algorithms can be employed depending on the nature of a problem and type of data. In the following, the details of two algorithms are provided that have been used to develop classification models for maintenance need and maintenance treatment of P&C.

3.1. Decision Trees

Decision Trees is a non-parametric method for solving learning tasks such as classification, regression and sequential decision making under uncertainty. It solves a classification problem by traversing from a root to a leaf node, while performing a test condition on non-terminal (i.e. root and non-leaves) nodes that separate instances of different characteristics. The leaf node then provides a class label for the instance under consideration. Generally, the decision tree model can be seen as a disjunction of conjunctions or as if-then rules to aid human interpretability. Furthermore, there are several algorithms available for efficiently learning a decision tree from the data such as ID3 (Quinlan, 1986) and C4.5 (Quinlan, 1993). These methods employ top-down greedy search approach to find optimal tree model.

3.2. Random Forest

The random forest is a term for an ensemble approach of decision trees. The ensemble is a divide and conquer technique that is used to improve the classification performance. The key idea behind ensemble methods is that a group of weak learners can produce a strong learner together. Random forests generate many different decision

trees, where each decision tree gives classification or tree votes for the particular class, it then select the class with highest votes.

The algorithm is as follows (Breiman, 2001):

1. Get N bootstrap samples from the dataset.
2. For each sample generate unpruned tree, at each node instead of selecting the best split among all features, randomly sample M of the features, and select the best split among those attributes.
3. Do not perform pruning. Save tree as it is, alongside those built thus far.
4. Classify a new test instance by aggregating the predictions of N trees (i.e. with majority votes for classification problems).

4. Experiment details and results

In this section, details of model training, features used and results obtained for each of the experiments are provided. We conducted two set of experiments by predicting a) need of maintenance and b) maintenance treatments. The tree based classifiers are used namely, decision tree and random forest. The result of decision tree model is treated as the baseline, which was later improved by applying random forest.

4.1. Experiment A

The purpose of this experiment is to develop a binary classifier that is able to predict if a generated notification will be accepted for maintenance or not. For this purpose, we used three datasets i.e. *P&C asset register*, *P&C condition data* and *notifications* generated in the past. The details of data and ground truth are discussed in Section 2.2 and 2.3. Each of these P&C is uniquely identifiable by their *equipment number*. Similarly, each generated notification have its own unique identifier as well as it refers to the specific P&C by their equipment number. In order to link the attributes of P&C, their current condition state and number of notification generated for each P&C, we combined these files. The file generated because of join had 65 features (attributes) and 10,913 training examples (rows).

One of the main task for the ML model development is to perform feature selection. There are number of reason for the feature selection i.e. often data have duplicate features e.g. year of construction and age which can be removed, selective features makes the model easy to train and interpret, and with selective feature a resulting model is generalizable, thus avoiding the problem of overfitting. For our model, we perform the feature selection mainly by considering one question, i.e. 'which feature is generally referred to, when making a decision to perform the maintenance or not to perform the maintenance'. In this way, we were able to identify those features that play central role in the process of maintenance decision making while leaving the others out. The example of features that are left out for model construction are: geo coordinates, responsible work center, material, notification status, etc. In total, we selected 22 features out of 65, that are used for the training of the classifiers. These features mainly include problem type, problem element, reason of the problem, functional location of P&C, track type, technical details, age, etc.

For model development, we did not perform any kind of pre-processing (such as normalization) on categorical features, because tree based models are invariant to feature scaling as they are not affected by feature scales (Friedman, Hastie, & Tibshirani, 2001). Though, we process the textual columns to eliminate the irrelevant information. The lowercasing is performed on words followed by removal of special characters, numbers and English stop words from the text. Since, a model is unable to process the textual data, the categorical features were assigned with numerical codes. Specially, for a problem description and technical details of P&C columns, the term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf) were calculated. The tf-idf score is a statistical numerical that suggests how important a word is to a document. The total of tf-idf served as a feature value. Top eighty text terms with highest tf-idf score are selected and combined with rest of the features. Moreover, from the date column of the dataset (such as last inspection date), month and year are used as features and actual date is discarded.

4.2. Experiment B

In the second experiment, a classifier is developed to solve a multi-class classification that is able to predict which type of maintenance treatment will be performed. For this purpose, *work-order* data file (see Section 2.2 for details) is used. The *work-order* file consists of all the maintenance activities that are yet to be performed triggered either by planned maintenance or by notification. For the model training, we used only those work order that are triggered

by notification (termed as unplanned maintenance). By using the unique notification code with each work-order instance, we were able to create a combined file that consisted of problem type and cause (from notification file) and planned maintenance treatment (from work order file). This file was then joined with P&C asset register and condition data by their equipment number. Again, only those P&C were considered for which we had data of condition state, notifications, and work order, making the process traceable.

The feature selection procedure was performed similar to Experiment A, except for the features obtained from work order file. The features stating the start date, end date, created date were eliminated from the final data as these dates were not true reflection of reality. For example, for some instances, the start, end and created date were same. While, in reality the creation date must be when a work-order is created, the start date is when a maintenance is performed and end date is when a maintenance treatment has been completed. Due to these inconsistency, the date attributes were eliminated for further analysis. Among other data related problems e.g. missing values, duplicate columns, data skewness specifically for maintenance treatment was one of the main challenges. The skewness of data impact the learning ability of the model. It will predict the maintenance treatment with majority class instances (i.e. M47 in our case, presented in Table 1) more often than others. In this case, the maintenance treatment with M47-P&C maintenance had highest class representation with more than 9000 instances. Considering this, we have randomly chosen only 1000 examples for the maintenance treatment of type M47. Moreover, some of the maintenance treatments such as, level crossing maintenance, realign CWR joints, etc., which had training examples less than 20 were eliminated because of too few instances to train the model. In total, 6 different maintenance treatments were considered for which enough data was available. Table 1 shows the considered maintenance treatments along with their code. The final data consisted of 23 features and 1910 instances that were used for model training and evaluation.

Table 1: Types of maintenance treatment considered

Maintenance Code	Maintenance Treatment
M01	Hand/Cobra pack Inc. TRV defect
M02	Replacement of defect material
M04	Oil/Grease/shim/equalizing Joints
M42	P&C OTM Tamping maintenance
M44	Maintenance Ballasting/ Dumper
M47	P&C maintenance

4.3. Evaluation Strategy

The performance of machine learning models can be evaluated in several different ways depending on the problem specification. One popular approach is K-fold validation in which data is divided randomly into K folds (Friedman et al., 2001). The K-1 folds are then used for training the model and Kth holdout fold is used to evaluate model performance. The process is repeated K times and performance metrics are calculated at each iteration, which are then averaged to get overall performance. This method ensures that every data point is at least used once as training and test example. A stratified K-fold cross validation is a variant of the general version. It aims to have (approximately) equal representation of every class across each fold to get better estimate of the model performance.

Following the classifier's validation, number of performance measures are used to evaluate and compare the classifiers' performance. Such metrics give an indication of classifier's ability to correctly predict or classify new unseen data points. The definitions of few performance measures that are used in this study are following:

- Accuracy: It suggests how often the classifier has classified the instances correctly.
- Misclassification rate: This metric determines how often the classifier have misclassified the instances.
- F-Score: F-score is a combination of precision (specificity) and recall (sensitivity) measures (Sokolova & Lapalme, 2009). The precision specifies the number of correctly classified instances. In contrast, recall provides a number that indicates a majority of correctly classified instances without considering those instances, where predict label suggested 'yes' but actual data suggested 'no'. These metrics are combined to produce a single metric called F-score, which is the weighted harmonic mean of precision and recall.
- Kappa: It is a measure of how well the classification model performed as compared to how well it could have performed simply by chance. Formally, Cohen's Kappa is a degree of the overall agreement between

two raters classifying items into a given set of m categories. A kappa statistic can take value between -1 and 1 for complete disagreement and agreement respectively (Wood, 2007).

4.4. Results

In this section, the performance results of the classifiers for prediction of maintenance need and treatment are discussed.

Experiment A

The results obtained from decision tree model were treated as baseline, which were further compared and improved by random forest. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show confusion matrices, which present the performance of a classifier on a set of test data where the true/actual values were known. These confusion matrices show the results of simple binary classification problem i.e. if the maintenance was performed or not. The true labels are actual values in the data, whereas, the predicted labels are the ones predicted by a classifier. In Figure 5, the classifier correctly predicted that 7630 times maintenance was performed, which is true. While, for 862 instances classifier predicted that no maintenance was performed and in reality they hold true label, which means maintenance was performed.

Figure 5: Prediction of maintenance need using decision tree

Figure 6: Prediction of maintenance need using random forest

Table 2 represents the results of classification performance on the measure of their accuracy, misclassification rate, f-score and kappa. Though there is not a great difference in performance achieved, random forest does better than decision tree as it can be seen by kappa metric. It secured the accuracy of 0.87 with misclassification rate of only 0.12. Similarly, random forest obtained f-score of 0.92 and kappa of 0.59, which were slightly better compared to 0.89 f-score and 0.54 kappa value for decision tree model.

Table 2: Results of classifier performance to predict maintenance need

Model	Accuracy	Misclassification Rate	F-Score	Kappa
Decision Tree	0.84	0.15	0.89	0.54
Random Forest	0.87	0.12	0.92	0.59

Experiment B

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the confusion matrices representing classifiers' performance to predict maintenance treatment using decision tree and random forest respectively. Since there were more than two maintenance treatments, the matrices show the results of multi-class classification problem. The diagonal in each matrix shows the number of correctly predicted instances by the classifier. Most of the misclassification problem was noticed for class M47 and M42 (see Table 1). With decision tree, M47 has misclassification rate of 0.17 and M42 has 0.10. The random forest has relatively lower misclassification score with 0.13 and 0.09 for M47 and M42 respectively. For the rest of the classes, the misclassification score is less than 0.1. This could be due to the number of training examples, that were used to train the classifiers, and/or having more discriminant characteristic. For instance, M47 had highest number of training examples followed by M42, where M44 had least number of training examples.

True Labels	M01	64	2	1	18	0	27
	M02	4	52	0	0	2	36
	M04	1	0	115	1	0	9
	M42	16	1	1	436	3	76
	M44	0	1	0	3	32	9
	M47	22	42	19	89	12	816
		M01	M02	M04	M42	M44	M47

Figure 7: Prediction of maintenance treatment using decision tree

True Labels	M01	62	0	1	24	0	25
	M02	1	42	1	4	0	46
	M04	1	1	114	1	0	9
	M42	10	1	0	462	1	59
	M44	0	0	0	5	27	13
	M47	9	6	12	77	2	894
		M01	M02	M04	M42	M44	M47

Figure 8: Prediction of maintenance treatment using random forest

Table 3 provides the results of classifiers' performance on treatment prediction. Similar to Experiment A, the random forest model performed better than a decision tree with both values for accuracy and f-score of 0.83. Moreover, the kappa score is better for Experiment B, where random forest model has obtained the value of 0.74 compared to decision tree model's value of 0.60.

Table 3: Result of classifier performance to predict maintenance treatment

Model	Accuracy	F-Score	Kappa
Decision Tree	0.79	0.79	0.67
Random Forest	0.83	0.83	0.74

5. Discussion

The Machine Learning (ML) classifiers developed in this study make use of available data generated through the SAP ERP system. Random forest model performed better due to its ensemble in both experiments with the accuracy of 87% to predict maintenance need and 83% to predict specific maintenance treatment. Infrastructure managers, while making decisions regarding the maintenance need and maintenance treatments, can use these classifiers as an add-in tool. For instance, with each newly generated notification, the ML models can predict, if the maintenance should be performed. These predictions are made by classifiers as they have been trained on 100s of similar instances that model will likely see in the future. In addition, these models will bring efficiency in decision-making process, as enormous amount of notification can be labelled in few seconds as maintenance needed or not as well as with predicted maintenance treatment.

There are number of potential ways through which the generalizability (or predictive performance) ability of these ML models can be further improved e.g. by training even bigger model on large relevant dataset. With the models introduced in this study, we cannot specifically state when the maintenance should be performed. As, it would require the deterioration scale of an asset as well as a typical duration of single maintenance activity. Similarly, with these models we cannot forecast the number of notifications that would be generated in coming year. We had data of only last six years with increasing number of notification recorded each year. This could be, either, due to deteriorating state of assets over time or because of the gradual adoption of SAP ERP system in the railway agency. Due to the limited amount of data, it is difficult to develop a regression model that could predict the duration of maintenance and subsequently maintenance schedules. However, we can still make use of simple statistical function of mean to forecast the need of maintenance in future, as such forecasting can be helpful for the budget planning. For instance, by considering the number of notifications generated from 2013 to 2016, we can estimate roughly that around 2800 notifications will be generated in the year 2017 for P&C. With the addition of cost with each maintenance treatment, the budget of next year can also be estimated.

It is mentioned earlier, the data used in this paper is generated from SAP ERP system, which is currently being used in number of railway agencies, e.g. UAE, Russian, Bulgarian, Irish, and Croatian railways. The maintenance request process in SAP ERP (see Figure 2) is similar for all the railway assets irrespective of their type. Therefore,

the procedure used in this study can be adopted for different type of assets, while, using the data generated from similar maintenance request process. Among number of railway objects, we have chosen to work with P&C, because it is one of the most vulnerable object on the network and requires frequent inspection and maintenance. Moreover, P&C generated enough number of notifications and work-orders over the past six years, hence, making it possible to train and test two ML models reliably. It is important to mention that, the data and the maintenance request processes used in this study belong to an actual railway agency. We have anonymized the railway agency for the sake of confidentiality.

6. Conclusion

This paper has used the available data from a railway agency to develop two machine-learning classifiers in order to predict maintenance need and a maintenance treatment. The purpose of these classifiers is to facilitate the infrastructure managers during the decision-making process of maintenance planning. These classifiers are trained and tested on historical data, past decisions, properties of a railway asset and problems reported over the period of six years. The developed classifiers can be used as an add-in tool with the current computerized systems, where with each maintenance request, a model can show its own prediction(s) learned from the past data. This will bring efficiency in decision-making process of maintenance planning. The future work of this study will include the development of regression models that are able to predict and generate maintenance schedules based on the predicted maintenance need and types of maintenance treatments. Such regression model can be used by a railway agency for the budget planning as well as for the procession planning of the network. Another extension of this work could be to use of sensor data for the real-time monitoring of asset's condition state. Instead of traditional visual inspection procedures, with structural health monitoring data, sophisticated machine learning models can more accurately predict a condition state of an asset and can generate more accurate maintenance plans.

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